

STUDIES ON THIOPHOSPHORYL CHLORIDE AS A SOLVENT. PART I

BY RAM CHAND PAUL, KAILASH CHANDER MALEHOTRA AND GURDEV SINGH

An attempt has been made to exploit the potentialities of thiophosphoryl chloride as a solvent for chemical reactions. The results show that the Lewis acids are fairly soluble in this solvent. Neutralisation reactions between the solvo-acids and solvo-bases have been studied and complexes formed have been isolated and analysed.

In view of phosphoryl chloride being quite extensively studied as a non-aqueous solvent, an endeavour has been made to explore the potentialities of thiophosphoryl chloride as a solvent for chemical reactions. Thiophosphoryl chloride hydrolyses more slowly than phosphoryl chloride and yields phosphoric acid, hydrochloric acid, hydrogen sulphide and, perhaps, a little sulphur, which makes the solution slightly turbid.

Its dielectric constant (5.8 at 21.5°; cf. acetic acid, 6 at 25° and carbonyl chloride, $4.34 \pm 0.02^\circ$ at 22°) and easy working range (m. p. -35° to b.p. 125°) make its study as a solvent quite convenient. The electron diffraction data for thiophosphoryl chloride (Beach and Stevenson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 6, 75) show that its structure is the same as that of its oxygen analogue. Radio-chlorine exchange reactions (Masters, Potters, Asher and Norris, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 4252; Lewis and Sowerby, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 336) have confirmed the ionisation of phosphoryl chloride as:

By analogy, it can be safely assumed that thiophosphoryl chloride ionises as

As a first step towards the study of this solvent, the solubilities of a number of substances have been determined quantitatively at $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results recorded in Table I show that the Lewis acids are fairly soluble in thiophosphoryl chloride. The production of coloured solutions in some of these cases is indicative of the formation of complexes in solution. Strongly electrovalent chlorides are insoluble, and this fits in well with the common observation that in solvents with low dielectric constants, the covalent compounds are more soluble than the electrovalent ones. Qualitative tests have shown that the solubilities of the trichlorides of antimony, iron, bismuth and aluminium in thiophosphoryl chloride increase with rise in temperature. A qualitative study of the solubilities also reveals that dimethylaniline and γ -picoline are very soluble; quinoline, pyridine, α -picoline, β -picoline and antimony pentachloride are moderately soluble; while zirconium and tellurium tetrachlorides are only slightly soluble in this solvent.

TABLE I

Solubilities of chlorides in thiophosphoryl chloride at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

Chlorides.	Solubility (g./100 g. of solvent).	Colour of soln.	Chlorides.	Solubility (g./100 g. of solvent).	Colour of soln.
AlCl_3	30.65	Light yellow	FeCl_3	7.26	Greenish red
SnCl_4	Miscible	Colorless	AsCl_3	Miscible	Colorless
NaCl	Insoluble	"	NH_4Cl	Insoluble	"
SbCl_3	125.30	"	BaCl_2	Insoluble	"
TiCl_4	Miscible	Yellow	BiCl_3	0.52	"
KCl	Insoluble	Colorless	DCl_3	Miscible	"
LiCl	Insoluble	"			

N.B. Insoluble refers to a solubility of less than 0.1%

Formation of Solvates.—A number of compounds were studied for the purpose of solvate formation in thiophosphoryl chloride, but only aluminium chloride and antimony pentachloride have been found to furnish monosolvates. Aluminium chloride dissolves in thiophosphoryl chloride on heating. On cooling the saturated solution, a yellowish white crystalline monosolvate, $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{PSCl}_2$, separates out (m.p. 115° , decomp.). Antimony pentachloride forms a reddish brown crystalline monosolvate, $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{PSCl}_2$, when the two liquids are mixed (m.p. 101° , decomp.).

Stannic chloride, titanium tetrachloride, arsenic trichloride and boron trichloride are miscible with thiophosphoryl chloride in all proportions. All efforts to separate any solid solvates were unsuccessful. Antimony trichloride, although highly soluble in thiophosphoryl chloride, does not yield any solvate. Pure crystals of antimony trichloride separate out when its saturated solution in the solvent is cooled. Zirconium tetrachloride, tellurium tetrachloride, bismuth trichloride and ferric chloride, which are slightly soluble, also do not furnish any solvates with this solvent. Sulphur trioxide reacts chemically with the solvent, resulting in the separation of sulphur. It was also not possible to isolate the solid solvates of quinoline, pyridine, α -, β - and γ -picolines and dimethylaniline, although some of them developed a slight turbidity in solution with thiophosphoryl chloride.

Acid-base Neutralisation Reactions.—On the basis of the assumption that thiophosphoryl chloride ionises, as indicated above, all substances, which on dissolution in this solvent increase the concentration of PSCl_2^+ , will act as acids and those which increase the concentration of Cl^- will act as bases. Lewis acids, e.g., antimony pentachloride, antimony trichloride, aluminium chloride, stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride, which have a tendency to increase their co-ordination number, can combine with the chloride ions so as to release the PSCl_2^+ , and thus act as solvo-acids, whereas the organic tertiary bases, quinoline, pyridine, α -, β - and γ -picolines, which contain electron-donor nitrogen atoms, can combine with PSCl_2^+ and thus increase the concentration of chloride ions and act as solvo-bases in thiophosphoryl chloride.

TABLE II

Acid-base neutralisation complexes isolated in thiophosphoryl chloride.

Acid.	Base.	Complex isolated.	Colour.	M.P.*	% Metal.		% Chlorine.		% Sulphur.		% Base.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
SbCl ₅	Quinoline	(C ₉ H ₇ N.PSCl ₃)SbCl ₅	Brown	150-53°	20.36	20.37	47.68	47.50	5.50	5.35	20.37	21.57
"	Pyridine	(C ₅ H ₅ N.PSCl ₃)SbCl ₅	"	120-22° (d)	22.47	22.23	51.68	51.84	5.83	5.84	13.60	14.40
"	β -Picoline	(C ₆ H ₇ N.PSCl ₃)SbCl ₅	Reddish brown	142-43° (d)	21.32	21.68	50.67	50.57	5.54	5.69	15.85	16.55
AlCl ₃	Quinoline	(C ₉ H ₇ N.PSCl ₃)AlCl ₃	White	100-102°	6.25	6.24	49.10	49.05	7.53	7.63	30.25	29.81
"	Pyridine	(C ₅ H ₅ N.PSCl ₃)AlCl ₃	"	133-35°	7.36	7.07	55.80	55.75	7.98	8.37	22.12	20.65
SbCl ₃	Pyridine	(C ₅ H ₅ N)SbCl ₃	"	160-62°	39.46	39.67	34.92	34.65	25.52	25.48
SnCl ₄	Quinoline	(C ₉ H ₇ N.PSCl ₃) ₂ SnCl ₄	"	200° (d)	13.88	13.83	41.87	41.39	8.02	7.46	27.65	30.08
"	Pyridine	(C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂ SnCl ₄ .PSCl ₃	"	...	19.85	20.18	42.30	42.24	5.23	5.44	23.02	26.85
"	α -Picoline	(C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂ SnCl ₄ .PSCl ₃	Pale yellow	160-62°	19.05	19.26	42.33	40.32	5.20	5.19	32.95	30.18
"	γ -Picoline	(C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂ SnCl ₄ .PSCl ₃	White	180°	19.21	19.26	40.57	40.32	5.26	5.19	26.73	30.18
TiCl ₄	Quinoline	(C ₉ H ₇ N.PSCl ₃)TiCl ₄	Orange-red	210-15°	9.93	9.80	51.13	50.88	5.86	6.55	20.16	16.42
"	Pyridine	(C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂ TiCl ₄ .PSCl ₃	Yellow	175-79° (d)	9.15	9.25	48.12	48.02	6.01	6.16	30.01	30.57

*Melting points are uncorrected (d- denotes decomposition).

The structure of the solvo-acids and bases in thiophosphoryl chloride, just as it has been represented in acetyl chloride (Paul, Singh and Sandhu, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 315) and benzoyl chloride (Paul, Chander and Singh, *this Journal*, 1958, 86, 869), can be represented as :

where B represents all the tertiary organic bases. AlCl_3 is a typical Lewis acid and SbCl_5 and other Lewis acids also will behave similarly.

Neutralisation reactions between these solvo-acids and bases have been studied and the complexes, recorded in Table II, have been isolated and analysed. It has been found that antimony pentachloride, antimony trichloride and aluminium chloride act as monobasic acids while the tetrachlorides of tin and titanium act as dibasic acids. Some of these complexes, however, lose solvent molecules to yield desolvated products.

Antimony pentachloride forms a monosolvate, $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{POCl}_3$, with phosphoryl chloride (Gutmann, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1952, 270, 179). The Raman spectrum of this compound (Gutmann, *Monatsh.*, 1958, 86, 52) shows the presence of SbCl_6^- and indicates the structure of the compound to be $(\text{POCl}_2)^+ (\text{SbCl}_6)^-$. By analogy; the ionisation of $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{PSCl}_3$ in thiophosphoryl chloride may be assumed to take place as :

Brown crystalline complexes: $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{PSCl}_2) \text{SbCl}_6$, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot \text{PSCl}_2) \text{SbCl}_6$ and $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{PSCl}_2) \text{SbCl}_6$ are isolated when a solution of antimony pentachloride in thiophosphoryl chloride is allowed to react with the solutions of quinoline, pyridine, and β -picoline respectively in thiophosphoryl chloride. The reactions may be represented as :

Aluminium chloride, which forms a monosolvate, reacts with quinoline and pyridine in thiophosphoryl chloride solutions to yield white crystalline complexes, $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{PSCl}_2) \text{AlCl}_4$ and $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot \text{PSCl}_2) \text{AlCl}_4$ respectively. Their formation may be explained as :

A white crystalline complex is isolated when a solution of antimony trichloride in thiophosphoryl chloride is neutralised with a solution of pyridine in the same solvent. This complex after drying in vacuum was analysed. The results agreed with the formula, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot \text{SbCl}_3$. Its formation may be represented as :

On drying under vacuum, the complex loses a molecule of the solvent to afford the desolvated product,

Stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride have been used as solvo-acids in a number of non-aqueous solvents. In most of these cases they form complexes with organic tertiary bases or quaternary ammonium halides, which contain hexachlorostannate and hexachlorotitanate ions. Stannic chloride forms complexes of the formulae: $(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N.PSCl}_2)_2\text{SnCl}_6$, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2\text{SnCl}_4.\text{PSCl}_3$, $(\alpha\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{SnCl}_4.\text{PSCl}_3$ and $(\gamma\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{SnCl}_4.\text{PSCl}_3$ with quinoline, pyridine, α -picoline and γ -picoline respectively in thiophosphoryl chloride solutions. The reactions can be represented as:

The complexes formed by the last three bases lose a molecule of the solvent to yield the partially desolvated products.

Titanium tetrachloride on reaction with quinoline in thiophosphoryl chloride solution yields an orange-red acid salt, which has been analysed in partially desolvated form, $(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N.PSCl}_2)_2\text{TiCl}_6$. Its formation can be explained on the basis of the formation and subsequent desolvation of the acid salt, $(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N.PSCl}_2)(\text{PSCl}_2)\text{TiCl}_6$ under vacuum as:

With pyridine, titanium tetrachloride furnished a normal salt, which was analysed in a partially desolvated state, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2\text{TiCl}_6.\text{PSCl}_3$.

The conductometric studies in this solvent are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiophosphoryl chloride was prepared by the aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction of phosphorus trichloride with sulphur (Knotz, *Oesterr. Chem.-Ztg.*, 1949, 50, 128) and purified by repeated fractional distillation in a special fractionating column, the distillate being collected at a take off ratio of 1:5. Aluminium chloride was purified by subliming in a current of dry chlorine, while anhydrous antimony trichloride was purified by distillation. All other materials were purified by the methods described previously (Paul *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

The procedure adopted for the determination of the solubilities at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ was the same as described for benzoyl chloride (Paul, Bains and Singh, this *Journal*, 1958, **38**, 489).

Preparation of Solvates.—Antimony pentachloride (5 g.) was added dropwise to 20 c.c. of thiophosphoryl chloride, placed in a conical flask, fitted with a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride guard tube. The reaction mixture was stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. A reddish brown solid separated out with the evolution of heat. This was filtered in a dry atmosphere, washed with dry petroleum ether (40-60°) and dried under vacuum. The analysis conformed to the formula, $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{PSCl}_2$; yield 5.5 g. (Found: Sb, 25.64; Cl, 59.75; S, 6.24. $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{PSCl}_2$ requires Sb, 25.91; Cl, 60.55; S, 6.83%).

Anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) was dissolved in hot thiophosphoryl chloride (20 c.c.). The solution was filtered hot in a dry atmosphere and allowed to cool, when a yellowish white crystalline solid separated out. This was filtered, washed with dry petroleum ether (40-60°) and dried under vacuum, yield 2.8 g. (Found: Al, 9.04; Cl, 70.19; S, 10.10. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{PSCl}_2$ requires Al, 8.91; Cl, 70.30; S, 10.55%).

Preparation of Neutralisation Complexes.—Equivalent amounts of the respective acid and base were dissolved in thiophosphoryl chloride separately. In general, the acid solution was added dropwise to the base solution in an apparatus, already mentioned under preparation of solvates. In the case of complex formation with antimony pentachloride, however, a reverse procedure was followed. The solid, thus separated, was filtered in a dry atmosphere, washed successively with thiophosphoryl chloride and dry petroleum ether (40-60°), and dried under vacuum. For determination of the percentage of the base in the complex, a known weight of the complex was dissolved in 15 c.c. of anhydrous acetic acid, prepared for non-aqueous titrations. About 0.5 g. of mercuric acetate and a drop of crystal violet indicator in anhydrous acetic acid were added and the solution titrated against $N/10$ perchloric acid in anhydrous acetic acid. A greenish blue colour indicated the end-point.

The acid-base complexes, thus prepared, are recorded in Table II along with their analytical data, colour and melting points, etc.